

TEACHING IN ALBANIAN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS *CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES*

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the role of regulations in promoting teaching improvement and career progression based on it in Higher Education Institutions in Albania. Obstacles and facilitators for enhancing teaching are identified, providing insights into the challenges and opportunities within the higher education landscape. Elevating teaching standards in Albanian HEIs involves addressing resource constraints, modernizing curricula, fostering pedagogical innovation, and adapting to changing demographics. A significant consideration is the language barrier; the absence of a language policy within Albanian HEIs inhibits the potential for study programs to adopt English as a medium of instruction, thereby limiting international exposure. Collaboration with industry, international partnerships, and a commitment to quality assurance can be key strategies for overcoming these obstacles and improving the overall quality of higher education in Albania. The paper concludes with a SWOT analysis, emphasising key strengths of Albanian HEIs such as the rich educational tradition that enhances teaching and learning quality. Additionally, the majority of the public HEIs that offer study program in education, also have established their centres for teaching

and lifelong learning, which can be a good support for staff development. An imperative recommendation is for Albanian HEIs to invest in the professional development of academic staff as educators, alongside a critical review of their appraisal processes. The incorporation of these suggestions into the accreditation process is essential, including the identification of appropriate methods, standards, and criteria for evaluation.

Keywords: *teaching, pedagogy, higher education, Albania*

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The Albanian approach to enhancing teaching primarily focuses on the pre-university level. Traditionally, teacher competencies are appraised mostly and usually at the pre-university level. Key strategic documents and laws that shape this approach include:

- Appraisal of the Pre-University Education Strategy 2014-2020, FINAL REPORT (UNICEF, 2019).
- National Strategy for Vocational Education Training and Lifelong Learning (2013-2020), prepared by 2012 year (MES & MLSAEO, 2012).
- National Strategy for Development and Integration, 2015-2020 (Council of Ministers, 2016).
- Educational National Strategy 2021-2026 (UNICEF, 2019).
- Law on pre-university education (KSH, 2012).

The most significant strategic documents and laws that supervise the quality in higher education, are:

- Law 80/2015 “On Higher Education and Scientific Research in Higher Education Institutions in the Republic of Albania” (KSH, 2015).
- National Strategy for Development and Integration, 2015-2020 (KM, 2016).
- Quality Code (ASCAL, 2021).

According to Law 80/2015, the state’s role is to assess the quality and functioning of higher education institutions through its agencies, whether independent or foreign, and make the process and its results public. This process is known as accreditation, which is an independent external quality assessment determining whether the higher education institution and its offered study programs meet specific quality standards in line with applicable legal and regulatory provisions.

External quality assurance is overseen by Quality Assurance Agency in Higher Education (ASCAL), which cooperates and coordinates its activity with European counterparts. External quality assurance for each study program includes three phases: first evaluation, periodic evaluation and comparative evaluation. The results of these evaluations are made public by ASCAL. The validity of each institutional accreditation and study programs related to it cannot last more than 6 years.

According to the same law, “Internal quality assurance” is the continuous process of monitoring, evaluating, guaranteeing, maintaining and improving the quality of activity in higher education institutions,

which is developed by the institutions themselves. At institutional level, one of the functions of the Academic Senate, is quality assurance and to create mechanisms for evaluating the teaching and research-scientific activity of the academic staff. In addition to the law, every higher education institution has a permanent committee for internal quality assurance. Scientific activity is also seen as a function of ensuring the quality of teaching. Students have the right to express their opinion about the quality of teaching. More specifically, this law has a chapter (Chapter X) on “Quality assurance in higher education”.

Standards for quality assurance are drawn up by higher education institutions, in accordance with the “Quality code”, Approved by decision No. 824, dated 24.12.2021¹ - a summary of standards and guidelines for internal and external quality assurance in higher education.

The Quality Code of Higher Education², in session III “Study programs, teaching and assessment”, standard 12, states: the institution follows a clear policy for improving the quality of teaching. This standard contains three assessment criteria:

- The institution is responsible for the quality of teaching and designs a regulatory/guideline framework in relation to it.
- The institution has an auxiliary structure that promotes the continuous completion of teaching.
- The institution qualifies/trains academic staff in the field of scientific research to help further improve teaching. For bachelor’s study programs and

¹ This decision repeals decision No. 531, dated 11.9.2018, in an effort to align it (partially) with the new quality code in higher education with the recommendation of the Council of Europe (2017 / C 189/03, dated May 22, 2017 “On the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning and the repeal of the recommendation of the European Parliament and the Council of April 23, 2008, on the establishment of the European Qualifications Framework for lifelong learning”. <https://www.ascal.al/media/documents/legjislacioni/VKM%20Nr.824,%20date%2024.12.2021%20Per%20miratimin%20e%20Kodit%20te%20Cilesise%20se%20Arsimit%20te%20Larte.pdf>

² Official Bulletin, Year 2018, Number 135. Quality Code of Higher Education

those of the second cycle the main aim is to promote competence-based learning. Responsible structures and units support experimentation and development of new innovative teaching methods, continuously train academic staff to improve teaching skills and implement new methods.

Methodology

This study is based on the qualitative method. The first step was to inquiry, through official pages published online, in order to find official sources relevant for the aim of this paper, deriving from the HEIs and listed in this way: strategy for enhancement of teaching; reports regarding internal quality assurance; the existence of a Centre for teaching and learning and its vision and mission; news regarding activities focusing in training. Those documents produced the main information. However, a great consideration was for the entire official pages of the HEIs, in order to establish conclusions in a wider context.

In the case of University “Aleksandër Moisiu” Durrës, based on the data found on line, a focus group method was selected, with two full academic staff. The aim was to build up a detailed perspective on how the centre for learning and teaching operate and also to bring what both deem to be important and significant. It was only one session, which was recorded and subsequently transcribed. Both participants were asked on how the CTL operates, and the role in enhancing teaching for academic staff.

Teaching enhancement

In the context of higher education in Albania, quality is primarily associated with the accreditation of study programs offered

by higher education institutions. There is no national strategy specifically dedicated to teaching in higher education. At best, the quality of teaching is subject to evaluation based on standards and criteria that can be considered external to the daily classroom experience.

In higher education, the main achievements, according to National Strategy for Development and Integration (2015-2020), consisted in the implementation of the reformed 3-cycle studies. Despite the introduction of a number of standards over the years, expansion and development of the education sector proceeded in a fragmented manner (Council of Ministers, 2016). According to the same document, forty-four private and fifteen public higher education institutions failed to meet the minimum requirements, as established in the law on higher education. Furthermore, the curricula are not adequately harmonized at the national level.

Meantime, it is important to emphasise, that some HEIs, mostly public, that have a faculty of education also operate a Center for Lifelong Learning. These centers offer training programs.³ All these programs receive approval from the Albanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Pre-University (ASCAP) and the Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) following an application process. The primary objective of these centers is to provide training programs for pre-university level teachers, rather than their own academic staff.

For instance, at the University of Gjirokastra “Eqerem Çabej”, an Albanian public HEI, operates a Center for Lifelong Learning (UOGJ, 2023) that exclusively offers training programs for pre-university education teachers. These training courses are fee-based, with the cost determined by credits (1 credit = 11 euros).

³ Private Albanian HEIs also offer training programs, typically targeting teachers within the pre-university education system.

Some of the training modules scheduled for May-June 2023 included:

- Comprehensive Strategies in the Classroom (2 credits)
- Identification, Prevention, and Intervention in Problematic Student Behaviors (1 credit)
- Preschool Education Curriculum Framework (2 credits)
- Designing Learning for Various Teaching and Learning Styles (2 credits)
- Project-Based Teaching and Learning (1 credit)

At the Marin Barleti, a private HEI for profit, there is a professional unit of comprehensive courses and trainings, under the name “Academy of Education and Teaching”, that offer training programs with the same focus and target (UMB, 2023). The national fee for one ETC (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) credit typically ranges from 15 to 25 euros, but the Center for Continuing Education charges 10 euros per ETC credit and 20 euros for 2 ETC credits.

Also, various HEIs host conferences with sessions focused on teaching in pre-university level.

For the first time, the need for enhancing teaching in higher education in official documents can be founded in a report of OECD. According to it, Albania needs to ensure that initial teacher education programmes are equipping future entrants with the student-centred approaches and other competencies they will need for the classroom (OECD, 2020).

At the institutional level, none of the Albanian HEIs has any strategy for teaching and learning for academic staff.⁴ In the best scenario, there are mentioned as part of institutional document for quality assurance. This is the case of University “Aleksandër Moisiu” Durrës.

At University “Aleksandër Moisiu” Durrës, special emphasis is placed on internal trainings that each faculty organizes with academic staff. At the beginning of every year, the Life Long Learning Centre in the Faculty of Education, with the support of the Department of Pedagogy, drafts a work plan for the internal development of academic personnel. The training topics to be conducted are decided based on questionnaires developed by the Unit of Internal Quality Assurance at the Faculty of Education in cooperation with the Dean’s Office (NjBSC Faculty). These questionnaires contain several questions directed at staff concerning the improvement of teaching quality and the need for training. Participation in these trainings is mandatory for new teaching staff, but rarely influence or help in passing successfully from one category of academic staff to another.

Teaching enhancement and career progression

In all Albanian HEIs, the academic staff engages in different activities, which usually are listed as: teaching activities, scientific research, support services for the development of the higher education institution and counselling for students.

Law No. 80/2015 ‘On Higher Education and Scientific Research in Higher Education Institutions in The Republic of Albania’, defines the categories of academic staff: a) professors; b) lecturers; c) assistant-lecturers. Career advancement for academic staff in HEIs is based usually on the above categories, where professors - a title that can be obtained based on some specific achievements - are at the top of the hierarchy.

While in the public HEIs the above rule is almost impossible to break, the private ones are more flexible regarding career progression, depending on the institution’s

⁴ Based on the documents published on line at the official pages of each Albanian HEIs.

culture, policies and visions. But even at the second case, career progression rarely is based on teaching enhancement. Usually, if one is holder of a PhD obtained abroad is evaluated as a valuable asset to advance in Albanian higher education system.

In general, there is not any relevance between teaching enhancement and career progression. The Albanian higher education system is not designed to support professional growth of academic staff as good teachers. Also, there are currently no specific regulations in Albania regarding mandatory training courses for entry-level teaching staff, or policies for staff development.

Discussion: obstacles and enablers for enhancing teaching and learning

Albanian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) are facing some challenges in providing high-quality education, from limited resources and outdated curricula to the need for pedagogical transformation and fierce competition mostly with foreign HEIs from region. In this session, the aim is to identify the obstacles, together with some suggestions for overcoming.

Obstacles

The main obstacles can be summoning under this list: limited resources, outdated curricula, pedagogical approach, faculty development, access to technology, Competition, Demographic Changes, Accreditation and Quality Assurance, Language Barriers and Lack of Research Culture. But, while is easier to address the obstacles, we cannot affirm with the same security the ways to overcome them.

Obstacle No 1: Limited financial resources

Many HEIs in Albania face budget constraints, which can affect their ability to

invest in modern teaching methods, technology, and faculty development.

Suggestions for overcoming: Increased funding from both sides of this sector, public or state HEIs and as well of the private (for public or state HEIs those funding are the obligation of government); seeking partnerships with international organizations; exploring alternative revenue streams (for example, partnership with industry or other sector of economy that are suffering the absence of human resources.

Obstacle No 2: Outdated Curricula

Some HEIs may still have curricula that do not align with current industry needs, creating a theory-practice gap.

Suggestions for overcoming: Addressing this challenge requires regular curriculum reviews and collaborations with industry to ensure relevance, encouraging faculty to incorporate real-world case studies and practical applications into their courses; improving the professional practice: there is a lack of investments by universities to have more staff as supervisor for student practice. Usually, the Albanian HEIs apply the “expert approach”, that is to appoint one of the academic staff for a group of students, as supervisor. In general, the role of expert consists only in making an evaluation at the end of the practice, not helping in improving experiential learning techniques, setting personalised objectives or integrating theory with practice, because usually this course is under evaluating by the departments (Nathanaili, 2023).

Obstacle No 3: The Lack of Pedagogical Approach in Faculty Development

There may be a traditional mentality that teaching methods and pedagogy are necessary only in pre-university education. A lack of emphasis on faculty development can hinder the adoption of innovative teaching practices.

Suggestions for overcoming: Encouraging a culture of continuous improvement in teaching methods, which includes faculty development programs and establishing of CTLs, can help overcome this obstacle. HEIs can overcome this by investing in training and workshops for faculty to enhance their pedagogical skills, mostly through CTLs; share best practices and success stories among faculty to inspire change; develop online learning platforms and resources to support remote and blended learning.

Obstacle No 4:

Insufficient access to technology

Insufficient access to modern technology and digital resources can limit the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

Suggestions for overcoming: HEIs should prioritize technology infrastructure improvements and ensure that both students and faculty have access to necessary tools.

Obstacle No 5:

Competition

Competition inside the country and from other European and global HEIs is becoming a challenge. This mostly means competing for funds and students.

Suggestions for overcoming: Albanian HEIs can focus on improving their ranking through research and international collaborations.

Obstacle No 6:

Demographic Changes

A declining youth population can lead to reduced enrolments, impacting funding.

Suggestions for overcoming: HEIs should consider diversifying their offerings, such as offering online courses or targeting international students to maintain or increase enrolments; implement scholarship and incentive programs to attract and retain students.

Obstacle No 7:

Accreditation and Quality Assurance

Ensuring that HEIs meet international quality standards is crucial for attracting students and resources.

Suggestions for overcoming: Overcoming obstacles in this area involves accreditation processes from well-known foreign agencies and ensuring continuous quality improvement; strengthen internal quality assurance mechanisms for continuous improvement, with a new shift, from identification to improvement.

Obstacle No 8:

Language Barriers

In a globalized education landscape, language proficiency is essential.

Suggestions for overcoming: HEIs can address this by offering language support programs and increasing the availability of courses in English or other widely spoken languages for academic staff. None of the Albanian HEIs offer teaching foreign language for students and staff, in form of extra classes, for free. For example, Catholic University “Our Lady of Good Counsel”, has a language center, that organises and offers foreign language courses of different levels under the Common European Framework of References for Languages (CEFRL), but those are with a fee (UNIZKM, 2023). There are a few HEIs that offer study programs in foreign language, like Epoka University and Catholic University “Our Lady of Good Counsel”.

Obstacle No 9:

Lack of Research Culture

Developing a strong research culture can enhance teaching and learning quality.

Suggestions for overcoming: Encouraging faculty to engage in research and providing incentives for publication; promote a research-oriented mindset among students through mentorship and research opportunities.

Facilitators

In order to make the difference we need to foster a culture of continuous improvement in teaching; to encourage faculty and administrators to prioritize and value pedagogical excellence. We have to invest in ongoing professional development for faculty; provide workshops, training programs, and resources to help academic staff to stay updated with best practices in teaching.

Conclusions and swot analyses

Enhancing teaching in Albanian HEIs involves addressing resource limitations, modernizing curricula, promoting pedagogical innovation, and adapting to changing demographics. Collaboration with industry, international partnerships, and a commitment to quality assurance can be key strategies for overcoming these obstacles and improving the overall quality of higher education in Albania.

SWOT analysis

Strengths

- The updated legal basis in accordance with the European one and the code of quality in Higher Education that forces institutions to work to increase the quality of teaching.
- Participation in international organizations and in the European Higher Education Area.
- ICT skills in the use of technology in effective teaching and learning.
- Public higher education institutions, which have faculties of education, also have centres for teaching and lifelong learning.
- A rich tradition of Albanian Education system that enhances teaching and learning quality.

Weakness

- HEI administrators are seen as weak links in the system. The need is to strengthen and improve the education management system with particular emphasis on building the systems to include establishing of CTL.
- The absence of quality researchers: Albanian universities are known for the absence of quality research and innovations.
- Institutions has indicators to assess quality, but no a definition of quality.
- The projects supported by the European Union are usually for capacity building.
- Many HEIs face financial constraints, affecting infrastructure and resource allocation, including the operation of CTLs.
- Inequality (HEIs located in Tirana versus those in other cities): There's a disparity in quality assurance implementation across HEIs, with some lacking adequate resources for improvement.
- Foreign Language is a barrier for most of the HEI academic staff, impacting their overall experience. The Albanian HEIs has not a language policy, to give study programs a more international profile by considering the option of English as a medium of instruction.
- Inadequate mentoring system during professional practice, which deepen the gap between the skills that the study program provides and the requirements of the labor market (Nathanaili, 2023).
- Mobility programs in frameworks of Erasmus+ programs are usually one-direction: the number of students enrolled in Albanian HEIs that goes for a certain period in a host foreign HEI is larger than vice versa.

Opportunities

- Development of blended learning courses appropriate for pedagogues

at different level of their carriers to provide training in specific methods of teaching and learning.

- HEIs can expand their global reach through collaborations, enhancing quality and diversity.
- The rise of online learning presents an opportunity for HEIs to improve accessibility and flexibility.
- Participation in European Union initiatives can lead to improved funding and quality enhancement.
- Establishing a national ranking can attract more international students and faculty.

Threats

- Theory-practice gap between curricula
- The inherit mentality that teaching methods and pedagogy are necessary only in pre-university education system.
- Other European and global HEIs pose stiff competition for students and

resources.

- A declining of youth population has led to a reduction of enrolments, impacting funding.
- Accreditation processes from well-known foreign agencies have a high prize, usually not afforded from the local HEIs.

Final remarks

The assessment of the quality of scientific research serves as the primary criterion for ranking scientific research institutions. Albanian Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) need to make investments in the professional development of their academic staff as educators and also need to review their appraisal processes. The incorporation of these suggestions into the accreditation process is essential, including the identification of appropriate methods, standards, and criteria for evaluation.

REFERENCES

- Agjencia e Sigurimit të Cilësisë në Arsimin e Lartë [Quality Assurance Agency in Higher Education], ASCAL. (2021). *“Code of Quality of Higher Education approved by DCM no. 824, dated 24.12.2021”*, <https://www.ascal.al/en/quality-assurance/quality-code>
- Këshilli i Ministrave [Council of Ministers], KM. (2016). *“National Strategy for Development and Integration, 2015-2020”* https://www.dap.gov.al/images/DokumentaStrategjik/NSDI_2015-2020.pdf.
- Kuvendi i Shqipërisë [Albanian Parliament], KSH. (2012). Ligj Nr. 69/2012 *“Për sistemin arsimor parauniversitar në Republikën e Shqipërisë”* [For pre-university education in the Republic of Albania]; https://www.arsimi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/Ligji_Parauniversitar.pdf
- Kuvendi i Shqipërisë [Albanian Parliament], KSH. (2015). Ligj 80/2015 *“Për Arsimin e Lartë dhe*
- Kërkimin Shkencor në Institucionet e Arsimit të Lartë në Republikën e Shqipërisë” [Law 80/2015 *“On Higher Education and Scientific Research in Higher Education Institutions in the Republic of Albania”*], https://www.unitir.edu.al/images/dokumenta/Legjislacion/Ligj_80-2015_22.07.2015.pdf
- Ministry of Education and Science & Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Equal Opportunities, MES & MLSAEO. (2012). *National Strategy for Vocational Education Training and Lifelong Learning (2013-2020)*] https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/m/2F2ABAD2B5A1126EC1257B650030CA17_TRP%202012%20Albania_EN.pdf
- Nathanaili, V. (2023). *Professional passive practice mentoring system in study program ‘Teaching for pre-school education’ in Albanian HEI-s*. European Early Childhood Education

- Research Journal, DOI: 10.1080/1350293X.2023.2247590
- OECD. (2020). "Reviews of Evaluation and Assessment in Education: Albania" Supporting teachers' professional growth. <https://doi.org/10.1787/d267dc93-en>. https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/oecd-reviews-of-evaluation-and-assessment-in-education-albania_8814b2f7-en
- UNICEF. (2019). "Albania, for the Ministry of Education and Sports of Albania" [Strategjia Kombëtare e Arsimit 2021-2026], <https://arsimi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Draft-Strategjia-per-Arsimin-2021-2026-1.pdf>.
- UNICEF. (2019). "Appraisal of the Pre-University Education Strategy 2014-2020, FINAL REPORT", Lund/Prishtina/Tirana 2 July; <https://www.unicef.org/albania/media/2031/file/Education%20Sector%20Appraisal%20Document%20Eng.pdf>
- Universiteti Eqrem Çabej i Gjirokastrës, UOGJ. (2023). "Qendra e të mësuarit gjatë gjithë jetës", <https://uogj.edu.al/category/III>
- Universiteti Marin Barleti, UMB. (2023). "Akademia e edukimit", <https://btcc.umb.edu.al/akademia-edukimit-dhe-mesimdhencies/>
- Universiteti Zonja e Këshillit të Mirë, UNIZKM. (2023), <https://www.unizkm.al/posts/slug/kerkim-shkencor/en>
- Schindler, L., Puls-Elvidge, S., Welzant, H., & Crawford, L. (2015). *Definitions of quality in higher education: A synthesis of the literature*. Higher Learning Research Communications, 5(3), 3-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18870/hlrc.v5i3.244> <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1132898.pdf>